

Scenario	Scale parameter	RCP	ystrat-yend	GCM+RCP combination	Climate Zone	Crops	Hazard & Risk	Crop table		Plots	Comments
								whole	clipped		
5.1	0.5	2.6	2026-2030	model_choice=1	5	['maize', 'wheat', 'potato', 'rapeseed']	OK	√	√	agri land level	New workflow 17.12.2025
5.2	0.5	4.5	2026-2030		5		OK	√	√	agri land level	New workflow 17.12.2025
5.3	0.5	8.5	2026-2030		5		OK	√	√	agri land level	New workflow 17.12.2025

Scenario results

Scenario	Scale parameter	RCP	ystrat-yend	GCM+RCP combination	Climate Zone	Crops	Hazard & Risk	Crop table		Plots	Comments
								whole	clipped		
6.1	0.5	2.6	2046-2050	model_choice=1	5	['maize', 'wheat', 'potato', 'rapeseed']	OK	√	√	agri land level	New workflow 17.12.2025
6.2	0.5	4.5	2046-2050		5		OK	√	√	agri land level	New workflow 17.12.2025
6.3	0.5	8.5	2046-2050		5		OK	√	√	agri land level	New workflow 17.12.2025

Scenario results

